

Creation of Multimedia Software Products for the Subject of "Natural Sciences" in General Secondary Schools

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Abstract: Interactive elements and simulations are used to facilitate the learning process of natural sciences and ensure active participation of students. Software products consist of animations, 3D models, simulations, quizzes and tests, among which it is possible to visualize important concepts in each subject and offer practical experiences.

Key words and phrases: multimedia, interactivity, simulation, animation, 3D models, tests and quizzes, educational platforms, testing and evaluation, program improvement, presentation.

INTRODUCTION. In general secondary schools, the subject group called “Natural Sciences” aims to provide students with basic understanding of nature and its laws. These subjects mainly include the following:

Biology: In biology classes, students learn about organisms, their structure, activities, species, and their relationships with the environment. Biology helps in studying life processes in nature.

Physics: By studying physics, students understand energy, motion, radiation in nature, and their effects on substances. In these classes, students conduct various experiments and practices, observe various phenomena, and apply laws.

Chemistry: In chemistry classes, the composition, structure, properties, and transformation processes of substances are studied. This subject helps in understanding chemical phenomena in nature, and many experiments are conducted in laboratory conditions.

Geography: In geography, students learn about the structure of the earth's surface, geological processes, climate change, and the impact of human activity on nature. In general secondary schools, these subjects are usually taught in grades 5–11, and each subject has its own specific curriculum and program. During the teaching process, natural sciences are taught through theoretical lessons, practical exercises, and laboratory experiments. Also, interactive methods, multimedia technologies, virtual laboratories, and simulations are used in modern education. These new methods make it easier for students to understand the sciences and increase their interest.

MAIN TEXT. The main goal of teaching natural sciences is to develop logical thinking in students, increase their interest in nature, and form a scientific worldview. The creation of multimedia software products for natural sciences in general secondary schools is mainly aimed at making natural sciences teaching more effective in the learning process. This type of software allows students to organize the

learning process in an interesting and interactive way. Such multimedia software products help students better understand natural sciences - chemistry, biology, physics, geography, and other similar subjects - through various interactive tasks, virtual laboratories, simulations, and animations.

The following are important for creating these software products:

Curriculum and content selection: Collecting and organizing information in accordance with the school's natural sciences curriculum.

Technological tools: Using special software tools (for example, Adobe Animate, Unity, Unreal Engine, or special educational platforms) to create interactive slides, simulations, video and audio materials.

Interactive tasks: Demonstration games, tests, and exercises ensure active participation of students in the learning process.

Program testing: Testing the program with students and teachers, taking into account their opinions, and improving the program.

Such programs can significantly improve the educational process and increase student interest.

Collecting and compiling information in accordance with the school science curriculum is a multi-step process that helps to provide students with the necessary and correct knowledge. The following steps can be taken in this process: First of all, it is necessary to study the curriculum and standards approved by the Ministry of Education or relevant organizations. These programs clearly indicate what knowledge should be given to students in each grade and subject. It is necessary to understand what skills should be developed in each subject, what goals should be achieved, and what the main content of the subject consists of. It is important to choose textbooks, additional literature, and sources in accordance with the curriculum. These textbooks should be consistent with the curriculum and written in a way that is understandable to students. Additional information can also be obtained from science-related sites on the Internet, scientific journals, and books. When creating educational materials for natural sciences, the following special software tools can be used to create interactive slides, simulations, video and audio materials:

1. **Adobe Animate** - For creating interactive slides, animations and multimedia content. Using Adobe Animate, you can create simple interactive animations, laboratory simulations, demonstration tests and lessons. By exporting this program to HTML5, WebGL, or video, educational materials can be adapted for use on different platforms.
2. **Unity** - For creating interactive simulations and simulators in computer games and virtual reality environments. Unity is mainly used to create virtual laboratories and complex simulations for natural sciences. This environment supports 3D models and animations that enhance visualization, which allows students to study various phenomena in a realistic way.
3. **Unreal Engine** - For creating virtual reality and 3D animations. Unreal Engine is capable of creating a large number of visual effects and realistic images. This can be used to create interactive lessons and simulations in natural sciences. For example, it can be used to simulate natural phenomena, show the reactions of substances, or display geographical areas in 3D format.
4. **PowerPoint va Google Slides** - To create short interactive slides. Microsoft PowerPoint or Google Slides are used to create interactive quizzes, quick polls, and animated instructions for students. It is also possible to integrate slides that support the HTML5 format, which makes it easier to present materials on online learning platforms. Demonstration games, tests, and exercises are very effective in ensuring the active participation of students in the learning process. Their advantage is that students actively absorb knowledge through interactive materials, develop logical thinking and problem-solving skills. Below are recommendations on the types of such tools and how to use them.

1. **Demonstration games Role-playing games:** Provide an opportunity to study various topics in natural sciences in a lively way. For example, in ecology or biology lessons, students can observe plant or animal life and observe how they change under different conditions.

Puzzles and additional games: For example, creating puzzles on the correct placement of natural science structures (organisms, organs or chemical molecules). This helps students understand the structure of matter or biological systems.

Simulating scenes: For example, through games that show the conditions around a volcano or games that simulate natural phenomena, students can understand how a particular event develops.

2. **Tests. Interactive quizzes and surveys:** Various tests and quizzes can be created on platforms such as Google Forms, Kahoot!, Quizizz. They provide quick results and encourage students to actively participate in the lesson. Tests allow you to check how much knowledge students have on the topic and give them the necessary advice.

When creating an interactive science program, it is very important to test it, as this allows you to assess its effectiveness and how useful it is to students. The following are the main steps for organizing the testing process and improving the program:

Student group: The program should be tested with different students in different grades and age groups. This will help to assess how suitable the program is for each grade.

Teacher group: Teachers of various subjects, especially science teachers, evaluate how the program can be used and recommend how it can be used in the teaching process.

A special scenario is prepared to practically test all the functions and materials available in the program. In this scenario, various aspects of the program, including interactive elements, tests and exercises, are tested.

In-class application: Carrying out the testing process in real lessons allows you to see how students perceive the program, their interest and level of interactivity. Students who have used the program can be asked about the attractiveness, useful aspects, and problematic areas of the program by conducting a short survey or interview. They can identify parts of the program that are unclear or interesting.

Teacher feedback: Teachers should be asked about how easy and effective the program is to use in the classroom. They can make recommendations about shortcomings and additional opportunities identified during the learning process. Eliminate shortcomings, errors, and technical problems identified during the testing process. For example, redevelop elements that students find difficult to understand or minor glitches in the system. Based on feedback, add new features to the program, such as additional interactive elements, the ability to choose the level of difficulty, virtual experiences, or other multimedia content.

Make changes to the program interface to make it more understandable and convenient for students and teachers. Add a short guide, interactive explanations, or remote assistance on using the program. Test the improved version again to check whether previous problems have been solved and the effectiveness of new functions. Repeat this process to further improve the program. This process increases the effectiveness of the program and creates an opportunity for students to learn in a clear and interesting way.

The goal of creating multimedia software products for the subject "Natural Sciences" is to create an opportunity for students to learn natural sciences interactively and visually. Multimedia software products facilitate understanding of subjects, attract students to active participation, and improve the quality of their knowledge acquisition. Such programs can consist of various content, including animations, simulations, video and audio materials, tests, and interactive games.

The main stages of creating multimedia software products:

Defining the goals and objectives of the program. Make learning science fun and easy for students. This helps to transfer knowledge from theoretical to practical. Helping students master the basic concepts of

science through interactive simulations, tests, and visual content.

Create and structure content. Select materials in accordance with the curriculum. Plan the structure of each lesson by topic, as well as cover the basic concepts of biology, physics, chemistry, and geography. Create or select animations, audio-visual materials, and tests that are relevant to the topics.

Creating interactive elements and simulations. For example, simulating chemical reactions or physical phenomena in a way that is close to real life. Platforms such as Unity or Unreal Engine can be used. Creating interactive biological structures, physical processes or chemical reactions using programs such as Adobe Animate or After Effects. Creating 3D models of various biological or chemical structures to further expand understanding of nature. Programs such as Blender or Tinkercad can be used.

Adding tests and games. Short tests, quizzes, for example, are created to test students' knowledge on an online platform such as Kahoot! or Quizizz. Games such as quizzes and puzzles. For example, preparing games that explain the structure of organisms or natural phenomena.

Creating and coding a multimedia program. Creating a user-friendly interface for the student by combining content. It is important to structure lessons, place games, simulations and tests in this interface. Using HTML5, JavaScript, Unity, or special educational platforms. Creating the ability to add to platforms such as Moodle, Google Classroom.

Testing and improvement. Testing the program with teachers and students. Obtaining their feedback and improving the program based on them.

Advantages of multimedia programs

Involving students in the active learning process.

Deep mastery of concepts by linking theory with practice.

Easier understanding of complex concepts through visualization.

These programs help improve the modern educational process and increase students' interest in science. Creating interactive elements and simulations plays an important role in multimedia software products for natural sciences, as they facilitate students' visual and practical understanding of science. Through these elements and simulations, students are involved in active learning of science, mastering complex concepts through experience. Below is detailed information about the stages and platforms for creating interactive elements and simulations.

1. Identify the main concepts and topic. Before creating interactive elements for the program, it is necessary to determine which processes or concepts need to be simulated for each topic. For example, simulating the laws of motion for physics, showing the structure of a cell for biology, or showing the reaction of substances for chemistry.

2. Choose the platforms and tools to use. Unity: Useful for processes and laboratory simulations that are dynamic in nature. For example, showing energy changes, the interaction of different substances with each other in a realistic 3D environment.

Unreal Engine: For creating more complex simulations and high-resolution visual effects. For example, creating a volcanic eruption or geological processes in nature.

Adobe Animate: Useful for creating simple animations and interactive elements. For biology lessons, you can prepare animations showing the structure of cells or the process of photosynthesis.

Blender: Allows you to create 3D models and add visual effects. For example, creating human organs or molecular structures in 3D. HTML5 and JavaScript: For creating simple web simulations. For example, elements that visualize basic concepts in mathematics or chemistry.

3. Providing interactivity. Queries and additional information: By adding interactive elements to the simulation, students can change different conditions and observe the results. For example, choosing

substances during chemical reactions and seeing how they change. During the simulation, add additional questions or choices to determine whether students answered correctly. This gives students immediate feedback and allows them to check their knowledge. A brief guide or help information should be included with each interactive element or simulation. This makes it easier for students to use the simulation correctly.

4. Adding tests and exercises. After each simulation or interactive process, add a test or exercise that checks students' understanding. For example, questions or instructions explaining the processes in the simulation. Experimenting according to the field: For example, adding substances in chemistry and observing what reactions they undergo or interactively examining the structure of a cell in biology.

5. Testing and improving. Testing the created simulations and interactive elements, obtaining feedback from students and teachers. Based on them, correcting technical or visual shortcomings and simplifying the interface. According to the suggestions, the simulation can be expanded or additional functions can be added. Interactive elements and simulations allow students to deeply understand knowledge, arouse interest in science, and master science through experience.

CONCLUSION. Multimedia programs in natural sciences For teachers and students working in natural sciences, multimedia software products serve as a successful tool for taking the educational process to a new level, increasing interest in learning knowledge, and introducing interactive teaching methods.

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